

Alfred Russel Wallace Notes 34.

Did Alfred Russel Wallace's Chief Assistant from His Expedition to the Malay Archipelago Really Name Himself Ali Wallace?

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Summary: In 1907, Thomas Barbour met Alfred Russel Wallace's former chief assistant Ali on Ternate Island, Indonesia. Ali apparently told him that he had adopted "Wallace" as his second name. This claim has been questioned by historian John van Wyhe and anthropologist Gerrell Drawhorn, probably because it appeared unprecedented. However, this was not an isolated example; in 1872, John Thomas Cockerell recorded that a man from the Aru Islands, Indonesia, employed by Wallace in 1857, along with his eldest son, had similarly adopted "Wallace" as part of their personal names. *Key words:* Alfred Russel Wallace, Ali Wallace, Thomas Barbour, Sarawak, Ternate, Aru, Malay Archipelago. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15075538

Who Was Ali?

In his 1905 autobiography *My Life* (Vol. 1, pp. 382-383) Wallace recounts:

When I was at Sarawak in 1855 I engaged a Malay boy named Ali as a personal servant, and also to help me to learn the Malay language by the necessity of constant communication with him. He was attentive and clean, and could cook very well. He soon learnt to shoot birds, to skin them properly, and latterly even to put up the skins very neatly. Of course he was a good boatman, as are all Malays, and in all the difficulties or dangers of our journeys he was quite undisturbed and ready to do anything required of him. He accompanied me through all my travels, sometimes alone, but more frequently with several others, and was then very useful in teaching them their duties, as he soon became well acquainted with my wants and habits. During our residence at Ternate he married, but his wife lived with her family, and it made no difference in his accompanying me wherever I went till we reached Singapore on my way home. On parting, besides a present in money, I gave him my two double-barrelled guns and whatever ammunition I had, with a lot of surplus stores, tools, and sundries, which made him quite rich. He here, for the first time, adopted European clothes, which did not suit him nearly so well as his native dress, and thus clad a friend took a very good photograph of him. I therefore now present his likeness to my readers as that of the best native servant I ever had, and the faithful companion of almost all my journeyings among the islands of the far East.

Ali seems to have entered Wallace's service in December 1855, when he was aged about 15 (Wyhe & Drawhorn 2015). Initially he was Wallace's cook and servant, but progressed to become his main bird collector and skinner, and eventually his chief assistant or "head man" (Wallace 1869). He accompanied Wallace for most of the remainder of his expedition, except possibly for two years (1 May 1859 to 1 May 1861)

Figure 1. The only surviving photograph of Ali, taken in Singapore in 1862. From Wallace (1905).

during which he was apparently employed by Wallace to undertake his own collecting trips (Wyhe & Drawhorn 2015). Ali married in Ternate probably in early 1859, and after Wallace departed Singapore for England in February 1862 it seems reasonable to assume that he returned to the island to live with his wife (but see Drawhorn 2016).

“I Am Ali Wallace”

In 1907 Thomas Barbour (1884-1946), a noted American zoologist, visited Ternate and accidentally encountered Ali, who was then aged about 67. He reported the meeting in Barbour (1921): “On the day of my walk to the Ternate lake an old Malay spoke to me; he had long forgotten his English, but he tapped his chest, drew himself up and told me he was Ali Wallace.¹ No lover of ‘The Malay Archipelago’ [Wallace’s 1869 book] but remem-

¹ Note that Barbour spoke Malay (Barbour 1943, p. 41).

bers Ali who was Wallace's young companion on many a hazardous journey. After my return a letter from Mr. Wallace speaks of his envy of my having so recently met his old associate." In his 1943 book *Naturalist at Large*, Barbour described the meeting in more detail:

Here came a real thrill, for I was stopped in the street one day as my wife and I were preparing to climb up to the Crater Lake. With us were Ah Woo with his butterfly net, Indit and Bandoung, our well-trained Javanese collectors, with shotguns, cloth bags, and a vasculum for carrying the birds. We were stopped by a wizened old Malay man. I can see him now, with a faded blue fez on his head. He said, "I am Ali Wallace." I knew at once that there stood before me Wallace's faithful companion of many years, the boy who not only helped him collect but nursed him when he was sick. We took his photograph and sent it to Wallace when we got home. He wrote me a delightful letter acknowledging it and reminiscing over the time when Ali had saved his life, nursing him through a terrific attack of malaria. This letter I have managed to lose, to my eternal chagrin.²

Were Barbour's Statements About Ali's Name Correct?

Wyhe & Drawhorn (2015, pp. 26-27) questioned Barbour's statements (Barbour 1921, 1943) about Ali adopting the name Wallace. They remarked:

As the attributed quotation "I am Ali Wallace" is . . . from memory; even though essentially the same as that given by Barbour in 1921, it may not be entirely accurate.³ It is unclear if Ali said this in English or Malay or that these were his exact words. It therefore cannot be taken for granted that he had adopted Wallace as his surname, as has sometimes been assumed. Indeed, Malays do not use surnames, but patronimials such as Ali bin Mohamed. Ali may merely have meant "I am Ali who was with Wallace" or "I'm Wallace's Ali." Equally it may be a mis-translation from the Malay by Barbour or his assistants. But it is impossible to know for sure.

Had this been the only case of its kind then these issues would need to be given full weight. However, the authors seem to be unaware that two other instances of Malay people adopting Wallace's surname have been recorded, which suggests that this may have been a cultural practice among people of the region to honour someone they highly admired. The cases in question were reported by John Thomas Cockerell (1819-1907), a commercial natural history collector based in Australia who travelled in 1871-72 with his son and crew to the Aru Islands in his schooner *Naturalist* to collect specimens. An entry in his journal for 1872 reads:

May 3. – Got under way 10 a.m., but wind dropping, we came to anchor again. The pilot [a local Malay imam] now gave us to understand that he knew Mr. Wallace well, and had gone with him to Wannumbai [in 1857]: also that he had great respect for "the Englishman,"

² The only surviving letter known from Wallace to Barbour is one in which Wallace expresses disappointment that Barbour had accidentally enclosed a photo of local men from Dorey [Manokwari, West Papua, Indonesia] in his letter, rather than the one of Ali he had intended to send (Wallace 1908). It is possible that Barbour subsequently send him the correct photo and Wallace replied to him in a letter now lost, which mentioned how Ali saved his life, no mention of which was made in his 1908 letter. Barbour's photo of Ali has not been found.

³ We do not know that the quotation was from memory, as it was a common practice at the time to keep a travel journal.

in consequence of which he and his eldest son had taken the name of Wallace. He showed us a heavy silver-headed cane he had received from that gentleman, and which he seemed greatly to prize. When my son told him that he also knew Mr. Wallace, and had seen him lately, the pilot and his son kissed us all round three times on the forehead, and the old man said that he would write a letter in the Aru language stating the time of visit of Mr. Wallace, and where he went and what he did. The pilot performed his promise, and gave me one copy and asked me to forward the other to Mr. Wallace out of respect for “the Englishman.”⁴ His notes were taken from a well-written and well-cared for manuscript book. He seemed to be a man of a good education, and took notes of everything new that he saw, or that interested him in our conversations. (Cockerell 1874)

Cockerell seems to have spoken Malay and his statement that the imam and his eldest son had both adopted the name ‘Wallace’ is difficult to dispute following the reasoning of Wyhe & Drawhorn (2015), since not only was Cockerell’s account written soon after the events he documents (so it is more likely to be accurate), but only the imam had been employed by Wallace. So given that two other Malays are known to have adopted Wallace’s surname as one of their personal names (see below), the case that Ali did the same appears to be considerably strengthened.

A Wikipedia entry entitled “Malay Names” (2025) states that although most Malays do not use family names or surnames, they may sometimes choose to include an extra personal name as a form of homage to people they admire. For example, “Some are taken from public figures around the world, such as Mohammad Rifae Zidane, whose third personal name is taken from the famous footballer.”

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⁴ Cockerell sent this document to Wallace (see Anonymous 1872). For a detailed discussion of it see Gallop (2017).

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